

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

ANALYSIS OF THE CODING METHOD TO INCREASE THE RELIABILITY OF INFORMATION

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Abstract

The work explores the importance of developing new encoding algorithms that meet the requirements of the modern era and creating new encoders that are more likely to reveal disinformation and eliminate distorted information in real time, guaranteeing data privacy and security, high consumer qualities, and therefore high efficiency of automation systems. Development of methods and algorithms using trigonometric functions to increase reliability of information support, as well as analysis of coding method are considered.

Keywords: algorithm, information, coding systems, key, trigonometric function.

Introduction

High quality of information transfer, storage and processing processes is achieved by solving data and software management, security and backup problems.

Information security is a structural set of all documents and information, i.e. information elements, stored and circulating in an automated system. In other words, information security is a set of a unified data classification and coding system, unified documentation systems, data flow schemes, and at the same time a database construction methodology.

The purpose of information provision is the timely formation and provision of reliable information for making management decisions. The main problem in this matter is timely, undistorted and safe delivery of information.

They also use different coding methods to ensure the security of information.

Many researchers have made significant contributions to the development of efficient information coding algorithms [1-6].

Material and methodology

In a Vernam cipher, the length of the key is equal to the length of the data, and the key is used only once. If we use a short, reusable key (which is relevant for most practical applications), then what is the best result in terms of code strength that can be achieved?

With zero information consumption, the uniqueness distance of the code is infinite. This means that even a short (or equivalently overused) key used to encode very long zero-cost data cannot be detected. This,

in turn, means that the adversary trying to open the encrypted text faces uncertainty equal to the uncertainty of the key. Obviously, this is the best that can be achieved under the given circumstances.

Let's look at an example:

Example 1. Suppose subscriber A has hidden important documents in a storage cabinet equipped with a five-decade combination key. Now he tells subscriber B the combination of numbers that unlocks the box. Subscriber A uses an analogue of the Caesar cipher [3] adapted to an alphabet of decimal digits:

$$c = (m + k) \bmod 10. \quad (1)$$

Here, m is the information symbol, k is the secret key, $k \in \{0, 1, \dots, 9\}$, c – is the result symbol of the encoded text.

Caesar cipher (lat. notae Caesarianae), displacement cipher, Caesar code, Caesar scheme is a cipher in which each letter in the plaintext is replaced by a letter in a certain fixed number of positions to the left or right of the alphabet.

Suppose subscriber A sent 26047 encrypted text to subscriber B. The adversary tries to decrypt it by successively trying all possible keys.

The results of the experiments are summarized in the table (Table 1).

Table 4.1.

Decryption of 26047 data by listing keys

k	m	k	m
1	15936	6	60841
2	04825	7	59370
3	93714	8	48269
4	82603	9	37158
5	71592	0	26047

It seems that all received options are equivalent and the opponent cannot understand which combination is correct. Analyzing the ciphertext, it cannot find the value of the secret key. Of course, before the data was intercepted, the adversary had 10^5 possible values for the code combination, and after - only 10. However, it is important to note that in the current case there are only 10 basic values. Therefore, with such a key (one decimal digit), subscriber A and subscriber B could no longer be trusted with confidentiality.

The reason the code is unbreakable is that all number combinations are valid, meaning there is no waste in the "language" of the combination code. Therefore, even simple code applied to data in this language is unbreakable.

$$H(x_1x_2\dots x_t | \bar{y}) = H(\bar{k} | \bar{y}) = \min \left\{ H(x_1x_2\dots x_t), H(\bar{k}) \right\}. \quad (2)$$

If the entropy of the key is less than the entropy of the source data, (2) simplifies and for sufficiently large values of the entropy

$$H(x_1x_2\dots x_t | \bar{y}) = H(\bar{k} | \bar{y}) = H(\bar{k}). \quad (3)$$

Since we are considering the case where the data length is large, we will use (3) as the definition of a strictly ideal code.

Informally, strict ideality of a code means that the number of solutions to a code sequence is equal to the number of different keys, and all solutions are equally likely.

From this position, we will evaluate the coding method developed on the basis of trigonometric functions, that is, we will try to evaluate whether a strictly ideal code is obtained as a result of designing using the above method.

Discussion and conclusion

First proposed by Lenore Blum, Manuel Blum, and Michael Shub, consider an ideal system evaluation approach limited to describing only the basic idea applied when the information is generated by a memoryless binary source with known statistics.

In other words, sequentially dependent non-random selection of letters is made on the condition that the selection probabilities of letters from the alphabet $A = \{a1, a2\}$ are known.

Suppose that a source generates data $x_1x_2\dots x_t, t \rightarrow \infty$ with a key of specified length $\bar{k} = k_1k_2\dots k_s, s \geq 1$. The entropy of the source for each letter is assumed to be equal to 1, because otherwise it is difficult to determine the quality of information encoding. We will sequentially divide the source data into blocks of characters of length n , where $n = 8$ is the number of bits in a byte. We will introduce some coding quality requirements beforehand.

Let's take a look at the requirements for coding algorithms in test automation systems. Whenever there is a question about the acceptability of coding sequences generated by test automation systems, ADS research and one or another stream code, it is necessary to take

Let's move on to the exact formulation of the problem. Suppose the data is encoded using the secret key $\bar{k} = k_1k_2\dots k_s$ and the encoded data $\bar{y} = y_1y_2\dots y_t$ is obtained as a result. Let us denote the entropy of the data by $H(x_1x_2\dots x_t)$, and $H(\bar{y})$ and $H(\bar{k})$ the entropy of the coded text and the key, respectively. Then $H(x_1x_2\dots x_t | \bar{y})$ denotes the uncertainty of the data and $H(\bar{k} | \bar{y})$ the uncertainty of the key, provided that the encoded text \bar{y} is known.

Definition 1. A code is called strictly ideal if

into account that the range of evaluation criteria for sequences is extremely wide.

Over the years of the development of coding systems, a large number of different approaches to analysis have appeared, but according to the American cryptographer M. Robshaw, each can be classified into one of two camps.

The first group deals with the evaluation of the statistical properties of the code sequence: is there any imbalance in the generation of the sequence that allows the analyst to guess the next bit with a better probability than random selection?

The second group of criteria allows the analyst to build his own sequence, based on the available gamma bits, which will repeat the coding sequence. In a sense, it explores the inherent complexity of this sequence and tries to answer the question - is this sequence difficult to replicate?

Aken together, the analysis methods described here are called by some authors a systems-theoretic approach to the development of stream codes [4]. The developer uses existing tests, and if any statistical weakness is found in any sequence class, a new test is developed and added to the suite. Obviously, this is a rather specific method of analysis, and many would prefer to have a more solid theoretical basis to justify the robustness of their stream code systems.

The quality coding process in information transfer systems of test automation systems and automated information systems is complicated by the uniformity of information transfers. The analyst understands the structure of the transmitted information. This makes the code-breaking process easier.

Therefore, a 6 MB source text was selected as a test for encoding. All text consists of a single character, 866 (ASCII, OEM, DOS) code table, which is the space character. This sign was not chosen by chance. When this character is bitwise decomposed, all bits have a value of 0. This type of text is very difficult to encode.

The stream method was chosen for encoding, which is not random. Stream coding methods are weaker than block methods, so they were chosen. By now, a very important theory already exists to justify the persistence of a particular stream code. But no matter how impressive the obtained theoretical results are,

the following remark always remains true: all the criteria established by the coding systems provide only a part of the conditions necessary for the stability of the coded sequence; a sequence may well satisfy all these conditions and still not withstand some new, as yet unknown, attack.

Coding systems of test automation systems and AIS have a limited data structure. Video, audio and image files are not transmitted through these channels. Information in test automation systems and AIS networks is limited only to the transmission of information related to the technological process.

Let's consider the test of statistics of byte combinations in encoding.

This test method implements directional mathematical coding statistics, the idea of the method is as follows.

Bütün yoxlama sistemi riyazi statistikada bir növ asılılıq tapmağa yönəlib. Bu, kodlaşdırmanı qırmağa çalışanların vəzifəsidir. Kodlaşdırmanın vəzifəsi isə kodlaşdırmada riyazi statistikanın olmamasını təmin etməkdir. Bunu etmək çətindir, çünki hər hansı bir kodlaşdırma müəyyən məlumat daşıyır və məlumat hansısa statistik xarakterə malik olmalıdır, bu qaçılmazdır.

In our case, encoding does not carry any information. In fact, the encoding, of course, carries information, but this information does not belong to the source text, but to the random number generator, whose operation is also influenced by the source text.

Let's look at the X-axis and the arrangement of bytes on the axis using an example. The letters of the Azerbaijani alphabet are used (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Byte layout.

Let's count all combinations of two letters found in the encoding. The combination of these letters is given below:

AB BC CÇ ... VY YZ
 AC BÇ CD ... VZ
 AÇ BD CE ... ÜZ
 AD BE ... UZ
 AE ... BZ
 .
 .
 .
 AZ

In addition to counting these combinations, we will also count the reverse combinations of the same letters.

In addition to these combinations, it is necessary to count the double combinations of each letter. For example AA BB CC CÇ ZZ.

After counting all the combinations, we make a graph. On the X-axis we draw all the combinations given above, and on the Y-axis we draw the number of combinations included in the coding. The number of combinations will not necessarily be equal to each other, and therefore they should be arranged in descending order. As a result, by approximating the points, we get a certain function, its shape is very important, in the best case it will be a sloping straight line, and in the worst case it will be a parabola. Coding can have different lengths, and in this case, the larger the coding volume, the smaller the unit piece along the Y axis should be compared to the X axis. In general, the size of a unit piece along the X-axis is constant, and along the Y-axis it has a variable size depending on the length of the encoding (Figure 2). 1 - ideal distribution, 2 - existing distribution, α - angle indicating coding quality. The smaller the angle α , the better the encoding itself. Ideally, $\alpha = 0$.

Figure 2. Angle α .

The ideal option is that the distribution density of combinations in the encoding is uniform for all pairs of letter combinations. Experimental data showed that the encoding quality is not affected by the source text and key length in any way. Only the coding formula itself has an effect, the mathematical statistics of the for-

mation of letter combinations, the frequency of distribution of these letters in the coding and all other characteristics of the code depend on it.

The results of applying the developed test to the proposed method and the DES method are given in a comparative table (Table 2).

Table 2.

Test results.

Parameters compared	Known method. DES	The proposed method	Ideal distribution
The type of encoded text.	6 MB of text consisting of initial bytes with 0 bit spread.	6 MB of text consisting of initial bytes with 0 bit spread.	6 MB of text consisting of initial bytes with 0 bit spread.
Distributive law. (Spectrum)	Normal.	Equally sized.	Equally sized.
The number of character combinations encountered in the encoding	25188	65536	65536
The number of repetitions encountered in the text	2-106;	2-85;	2-96;
Increasing the volume of encoded text.	8 byte	2 byte	No increase
Encoding time.	6 minutes and 20 seconds	25 seconds	
The total number of 0-s and 1-s in the encoding	1 - 25349346; 0-25232158; breakdown - 0.231682%.	1 -25159905; 0-25171743; breakdown - 0.023520%.	1 -25168277; 0-25163435; breakdown - 0.009620%.

As can be seen from the table, the proposed coding method is superior to the DES encryption algorithm [46] in terms of speed and coding quality, and inferior to random sequences. Compared to DES, the number of combinations has increased by about 2.5 times and approached the ideal system, the number of repetitions has decreased by 20%, the increase in the encoding volume has changed by 6 bytes, and the encoding time has decreased by 15 times. The obtained characteristics allow us to conclude that the method developed for this test is significantly superior to the standard DES method.

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